

UTILIZATION OF ICT LEARNING RESOURCES AND INSTRUCTIONAL DELIVERY PRACTICES AMONG SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

This study examined how teachers use ICT for instruction and as a learning resource. A survey was conducted among thirty (30) public senior high school teachers. The findings demonstrated moderate ICT use, primarily to enhance student creativity, access resources, promote literacy, facilitate classroom management, and encourage self-expression. Teachers used ICT less frequently to make lessons more engaging or to enhance learning outcomes and employed it modestly, relying on tools, laboratories, and skill-building opportunities, yet with limited infrastructure, support, and professional development. There were no significant differences in ICT use by age, education, or experience, indicating that teachers use ICT consistently across groups. The findings indicate that ICT is used to support teaching but has not fully improved learning, promoting the need for stronger institutional support and better integration of ICT into teaching methods.

Keywords: *instructional delivery, learning resources, senior high school teachers, information and communication technology.*

INTRODUCTION

The use of information and communication technology (ICT) is important in the modern educational system as schools shift from traditional to technology-supported teaching. Worldwide, ICT enhances instructional learning resources. The Malaysia Education Blueprint (2013–2025) (MOE, 2013) stresses the relevance of integrating ICT

into the curriculum. Technology plays a vital role in disseminating relevant information across sectors, including education, in transforming how we think, work, and learn (Grabe & Grabe, 2007). Schools should integrate ICT into teaching and curricula to prepare students for a knowledge society (Ghavifekr et al., 2012). Recent discussions highlight ICT's role in shaping teaching methods and classroom practices, beyond just educational results.

With ongoing digital transformation in the Philippines, sustained support is needed for teachers to effectively use ICT in their classrooms. Teachers are key to preparing, using, and aligning ICT resources with curricula. Teacher professional training workshops and institutional and instrumental support are important for improving practices and supporting the Department of Education. Moreover, a knowledge-based economy pressures schools to adopt new technologies and provide equitable access to digital resources (Bonifacio, 2018).

The Department of Education issued DepEd Order No. 78, s. 2010, to outline the DepEd Computerization Program (DCP). This initiative aimed to improve access to education by providing ICT infrastructure, such as hardware, software, and technical training. Partnerships between the government and the private sector have led to the installation of computer laboratories and facilities in thousands of public secondary schools. A DepEd press release in February 2025 reported that, through DCP and related projects, 1,253,919 devices had been distributed to 93% of public secondary schools by 2020. Additional procurement efforts included 36,676 laptops (DCP2020), 39,583 (Bayanihan II), and 65,683 (DCP2021), bringing the total to 1,385,178 devices nationwide. Recent reports indicate that over 1,828,196 computers have been provided to public schools at all levels, reaching more than 80% of institutions, including 598,332 for junior high schools and 720,489 for senior high schools. Approximately 838,618 devices—including 223,808 laptops, 124,939 desktops, and 489,871 tablets now support nearly 97% of DepEd's 857,310 teaching staff, enabling ICT integration in daily instruction. In 2024, the program fully procured 44,638 ICT packages, exceeding the revised target, with delivery completed by December despite budget constraints, including a P10-billion cut.

Despite nationwide efforts, teachers vary in their use of ICT learning materials. Researchers examined factors such as age, education, and experience to assess their differences in teaching and technology use. The OECD's PISA found that experience and background affect teaching effectiveness. Local studies have mixed results on education and training in teaching (Sumanga, 2022). Further research is needed to examine how demographic factors explain ICT use and instruction.

This study investigated how senior high school teachers use ICT resources and deliver instruction, examining differences based on age, education, and experience. It aimed to improve understanding of ICT implementation by analyzing actual usage rather than expected results.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess how senior high school teachers utilize ICT learning resources and their instructional delivery methods. Specifically, the study sought to answer these questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of public senior high school teachers regarding age, education, and service length?
2. How do public school teachers utilize ICT in instruction delivery and learning resources?
3. Are there significant differences in ICT use in instruction delivery and learning resources based on teacher profiles?

METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative descriptive research design to explore patterns and differences in respondents' perceptions. It was carried out in selected public senior high schools within the Division of Malaybalay City. A total of thirty (30) senior high school teachers from public secondary schools participated. Simple random sampling was employed to select respondents from a list of all eligible teachers in the division, ensuring each individual had an equal chance of being included and increasing representativeness across demographic groups. This method generated data reflecting diverse experiences with ICT learning resources and instructional practices. Respondent profiles included age, educational attainment, and years of service. Data were collected through a researcher-made survey instrument featuring sections on exposure to ICT in instruction and available resources. Responses were rated on a four-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Disagree (1) to Strongly Agree (4), a validated scale widely used in educational research.

To ensure instrument quality, experts and practitioners validated the content by assessing the relevance of the items to the measured construct. Revisions reflected validators' feedback and reliability results ($\alpha=0.820$). The final form of the instrument was administered in person after securing permission and informed consent. Respondents had adequate time, and all questionnaires were retrieved for data processing.

SPSS was employed to analyze the data. Respondent demographics and ICT usage were characterized using frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. Independent t-tests and one-way ANOVA were conducted to compare ICT use across demographic groups. The significance level was set at 0.05. This study was confined to senior high school teachers from selected public secondary schools within a single division, thereby limiting the generalizability of the findings. Data collected were self-reported, which may introduce bias, as participants reported perceptions rather than observable practices (Podsakoff et al., 2003). The study did not account for infrastructure, support, and outcomes, focusing solely on demographic variables. Despite these limitations, the research provides valuable insights into ICT use among senior high school teachers.

RESULTS

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows how respondents are distributed by age, in terms of frequency and percentage. The most common age group is 46–50, making up 33% of the sample. Next are respondents aged 41–45 at 23% and 36–40 at 17%. The smallest group is those under 25, representing only 3%.

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents' Profiles in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Below 25	1	3%
26–30	3	10%
31–35	4	13%
36–40	5	17%
41–45	7	23%
46–50 Above	10	33%
Total	30	100%

Table 2 displays the educational attainment of the respondents. The majority, 73%, hold a college degree, whereas 27% have completed a master's degree. No respondent reported possessing a doctorate degree.

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents' Profile According to Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
College Degree	22	73%
Masters	8	27%
Doctorate	0	0%
Total	30	100%

Table 3 shows how respondents are distributed based on their length of service. The largest group (47%) has 6–10 years of experience, while 33% have 1–5 years. The rest of the respondents have over ten years of teaching experience.

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents' Profile According to Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
1–5	10	33%
6–10	14	47%
11–15	1	3%
16–20	2	7%
Over 20	3	10%
Total	30	100%

The following tables present respondents' perceptions regarding ICT usage, focusing on student instruction and the design and implementation of ICT learning resources, which were collected and analyzed.

Delivery of Instruction to the Students

Table 4 presents the mean distribution of teachers' perceptions of the delivery of instruction to students using ICT (n = 30). The overall mean score is 3.22, with a standard deviation of 0.65, described as "agree" and interpreted as "moderately utilized."

Table 4
Mean Distribution of Teachers' Perception in Terms of the Delivery of Instruction Towards the Students (n= 30)

No.	Item Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1	...foster students' creativity and imagination.	3.53	0.51	Highly Utilized
2	...enable students to access relevant knowledge and learning information.	3.33	0.76	Highly Utilized
3	...facilitate communication and interaction among students.	3.07	0.78	Moderately Utilized
4	...encourage students' confidence and active participation in class activities.	3.30	0.60	Highly Utilized
5	...support students' learning effectiveness during classroom instruction.	2.47	0.73	Slightly Utilized
6	...broaden students' knowledge perspectives beyond traditional instruction.	3.47	0.63	Highly Utilized
7	...support the development of students' reading and writing skills.	3.50	0.57	Highly Utilized
8	...support classroom management and positive student behavior.	3.30	0.70	Highly Utilized
9	...enable students to express ideas and thoughts more effectively.	3.27	0.52	Highly Utilized

No.	Item Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
	<i>ICT is utilized in instructional delivery to...</i>			
10	...support the conduct of active and engaging classroom lessons.	2.93	0.74	Moderately Utilized
Overall		3.22	0.65	Moderately Utilized

Legend: 1.00–1.75 Strongly Disagree (Not Utilized); 1.76–2.50 Disagree (Slightly Utilized); 2.51–3.25 Agree (Moderately Utilized); 3.26–4.00 Strongly Agree (Highly Utilized)

Preparation and Implementation of ICT Learning Resources

Table 5 presents the mean distribution of teachers' perceptions regarding the preparation and implementation of ICT learning resources (n = 30). The overall mean score is 3.13, with a standard deviation of 0.62, described as "agree" and interpreted as "moderately utilized."

Table 5
Mean Distribution of Teachers' Perception in Terms of the Preparation and Implementation of ICT Learning Resources (n= 30)

No.	Item Indicator	Mean	SD	Interpretation
	<i>ICT learning resources are utilized to support...</i>			
1	...the availability and functionality of ICT facilities for instructional use.	2.73	0.69	Moderately Utilized
2	...the provision of technical support when difficulties are encountered.	2.90	0.66	Moderately Utilized
3	...adequate access to ICT resources for classroom instruction.	3.20	0.61	Moderately Utilized
4	...administrative support from school leadership for ICT-based instruction.	3.13	0.57	Moderately Utilized
5	...sufficient instructional time for integrating ICT into teaching and learning activities.	3.03	0.67	Moderately Utilized
6	...teachers' participation in training and professional development related to ICT use.	3.20	0.61	Moderately Utilized
7	...the availability and use of ICT tools for instructional purposes.	3.27	0.52	Highly Utilized
8	...teachers' opportunities to learn and become comfortable with ICT use in teaching.	3.33	0.55	Highly Utilized
9	...access to computer laboratories for viewing educational videos and digital materials.	3.27	0.64	Highly Utilized
10	...teachers' autonomy to design instruction with the support of ICT resources.	3.03	0.67	Moderately Utilized
Overall		3.13	0.62	Moderately Utilized

Legend: 1.00–1.75 Strongly Disagree (Not Utilized); 1.76–2.50 Disagree (Slightly Utilized); 2.51–3.25 Agree (Moderately Utilized); 3.26–4.00 Strongly Agree (Highly Utilized)

Difference in the Delivery of Instruction When Grouped According to Profile

Table 6 presents the test of significant differences in instructional delivery, grouped by profile. The computed p-values for age ($p = 0.302$), educational attainment ($p = 0.397$), and length of service ($p = 0.571$) are all greater than 0.05, indicating no significant differences. The null hypothesis was not rejected for any profile variable.

Table 6
Test of Significant Difference between the Delivery of Instruction when Grouped According to Their Profile

Profile	Utilization in the Delivery of Instruction		
	T-value	P-value	Decision on Ho
Age	0.839	0.302	Fail to reject
Educational Attainment	-0.842	0.397	Fail to reject
Length of Service	0.556	0.571	Fail to reject

Significant if p -value < 0.05

Legend: Ho is rejected if significant; Ho is accepted if not significant.

Difference in the Preparation and Implementation of ICT Learning Resources When Grouped According to Profile

Table 7 shows the test results for significant differences in the preparation and implementation of ICT learning resources based on profile groups. The p-values for age ($p = 0.957$), educational attainment ($p = 0.139$), and length of service ($p = 0.417$) are all above 0.05, suggesting no significant differences. The null hypothesis was not rejected for any of the profile variables.

Table 7
Test of Significant Difference between the Preparation and Implementation of ICT Learning Resources when Grouped According to Their Profile

Profile	Preparation and implementation of ICT learning resources		
	T-value	P-value	Decision on Ho
Age	0.104	0.957	Fail to reject
Educational Attainment	1.892	0.139	Fail to reject
Length of Service	0.540	0.417	Fail to reject

Significant if p -value < 0.05

Legend: Ho is rejected if significant; Ho is accepted if not significant.

DISCUSSION

Teachers' Demographic Profile and ICT Utilization

Most respondents were 41 years of age or older and had 6 to 10 years of teaching experience. Regardless of age, they consistently used ICT for both instructional delivery and resource use. This is consistent with current research, which shows that age no longer has a substantial impact on technology adoption in education due to continual exposure to digital tools and institutional mandates that close generational disparities in ICT use (Bond et al., 2021; OECD, 2023). Use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) did not differ by college degree, although fewer teachers held master's degrees. This supports previous studies demonstrating that access, institutional support, and professional development possibilities, rather than academic credentials, influence ICT usage (Koehler et al., 2020; Tondeur et al., 2022).

ICT Utilization in the Delivery of Instruction

ICT was employed moderately in instructional delivery, with increased usage in areas such as creativity, knowledge access, literacy, classroom management, and student expression. These findings indicate that teachers use ICT primarily to increase student engagement, improve access to learning resources, and promote communication, rather than to replace traditional teaching practices. Its importance in multimodal learning and differentiated instruction is supported by evidence of its significant impact on developing creativity, imagination, and reading and writing skills (Redecker, 2021; UNESCO, 2022). Presentations, films, and interactive content have all been shown to interest and motivate students, particularly in secondary education.

ICT (Information and Communication Technology) was employed in moderation to support peer communication, engaging lessons, and perceived learning effectiveness. Teachers recognize the importance of ICT in increasing engagement and providing access to information, but they are less inclined to attribute learning gains solely to ICT. This is consistent with recent meta-analyses showing that technology integration alone does not improve learning outcomes (Schindler et al., 2020; Tamim et al., 2022).

ICT (Information and Communication Technology) was somewhat used for peer communication, engaging lessons, and perceived learning efficacy. Teachers recognize the importance of ICT in increasing engagement and providing access to information, but they are less likely to attribute learning gains solely to ICT. This is consistent with recent meta-analyses demonstrating that technology integration alone does not improve learning outcomes (Schindler et al., 2020; Tamim et al., 2022).

Implementation of ICT Learning Resources

The adoption of ICT learning resources was moderate, indicating that basic frameworks for ICT integration are in place but not fully optimized. The moderate levels of functional facilities, technical assistance, administrative support, instructional time, and professional

development suggest a degree of institutional maturity in ICT adoption. These findings complement previous studies demonstrating that infrastructure alone is insufficient for effective ICT integration; ongoing technical support, leadership commitment, and ongoing professional development are required (Petko et al., 2022; UNESCO, 2023). Teachers made extensive use of ICT materials, gained confidence, and had access to computer labs; however, systemic supports, such as formal training and dedicated time, were inadequate. Teacher autonomy with ICT provides a favorable setting for instructional innovation; however, without instrumental support, ICT practices may vary across classrooms. This emphasizes the need for school-wide ICT plans that coordinate infrastructure, training, and learning activities (Tondeur et al., 2021).

Differences in ICT Utilization When Grouped According to Profile

It is worth noting that the implementation of ICT learning resources was moderate, implying that basic frameworks for ICT integration exist but are not fully optimized. The moderate levels of functional facilities, technical assistance, administrative backing, instructional time, and professional development suggest some level of institutional maturity in ICT adoption. These findings confirm research demonstrating that infrastructure alone is insufficient for effective ICT integration; ongoing technical support, leadership commitment, and professional development are required (Petko et al., 2022; UNESCO, 2023). Teachers made extensive use of ICT materials, gained confidence, and had access to computer laboratories; however, systemic supports, such as formal training and dedicated time, were inadequate. Teacher autonomy with ICT indicates a favorable environment for instructional innovation; nevertheless, without instrumental support, ICT practices may vary across classrooms. This emphasizes the significance of school-wide ICT policies that integrate infrastructure, training, and learning activities (Tondeur et al., 2021).

This is described by the diffusion of innovation theory, which emphasizes how ICT activities normalize over time, minimizing the gap between early and late adopters (Rogers, 2003; Straub, 2020). The survey reveals that ICT use has progressed beyond initial acceptance and is now routine. Senior high school teachers' ICT integration is functional rather than transformative; they use it to enhance engagement, creativity, and access while overlooking its potential to transform education. This suggests a shift from merely supplying ICT to pedagogically driven integration, aligning technology with learning objectives and instructional techniques. Given the minor demographic gaps, future efforts might focus on system-level professional development, instructional coaching, and leadership to promote the use of ICT in all classrooms.

Conclusions

The study found that senior high school instructors use ICTs for instructional delivery, resource planning, and implementation, regardless of demographic background. Most mid-career to senior teachers hold college degrees and have moderate teaching experience, indicating that ICT adoption is widespread in the context rather than limited to younger or more academically advanced teachers.

It should also be highlighted that the lack of significant variations in teachers' ICT use across age, educational attainment, and length of service supports a demographically consistent pattern of technology adoption. This indicates that ICT exposure, institutional expectations, and everyday professional contexts may exert greater influence on ICT use than demographics. This indicates that instructional practice has normalized ICT integration.

Information and communication technology was used moderately in education, primarily to support participation, organization, and access to materials. Teachers reported using ICT extensively to support creativity, resources, literacy, classroom management, and idea expression, but only minimally to enhance the effectiveness of active, engaging teaching and learning. Teachers are reticent to relate improved learning to ICT, citing instructional design as critical. There is moderate use of ICT resources and institutional support, such as infrastructure and training, but systemic support may be insufficient for more advanced integration. Overall, high school teachers commonly use ICT in education, but its potential to improve learning remains largely unexplored. Better support and instructional initiatives are required to increase ICT use above moderate levels.

Recommendations

School leaders can improve ICT integration by providing more instrumental support, focusing on infrastructure upkeep, technical help, and coordinated professional development. Providing ongoing pedagogical training, rather than merely technical capabilities, can help instructors better harness ICT to improve learning outcomes.

Teachers should consider pedagogically driven ICT applications, such as collaborative learning, formative assessment, and differentiated instruction, alongside content delivery and engagement. Incorporating ICT into effective instructional frameworks can assist improve perceived learning effectiveness, particularly in low-usage environments.

Future studies could include more schools or divisions to increase generalizability. Mixed-methods or qualitative approaches may disclose teachers' experiences with, barriers to, and opinions regarding ICT integration. Furthermore, longitudinal studies can measure how long-term professional development and policy actions affect ICT use.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author certifies adherence to ethical study norms, including obtaining informed consent, ensuring participant safety, protecting data privacy, and maintaining participant anonymity. There are no conflicts of interest or plagiarism. Following objective analysis, the results were only used for academic purposes. AI tools were used only for language editing, with little impact on the substantive intellectual content.

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